

1. Comparison of fingerprints obtained using DNA from *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* PX0112 prepared from cultured cells by the potassium acetate method (lanes 1 and 2) and from cells leached from infected leaves by the alcohol lysis method (lanes 3, 4, 5 and 6). Infected leaves were those of IR24 grown in the greenhouse, and the primers JEL1/JEL2 were used to generate the fingerprints.

sistent. Amplification appeared more efficient when DNA was released by lysis with alcohol, and cellular debris and other contaminants were removed prior to amplification.

To assess the general utility of the method, bacteria were also leached

2. Fingerprint patterns obtained from naturally infected leaves of IR24 (lanes 1, 8, 9, and 10) and near-isogenic lines IRBB4 (lanes 2, 3, 11, and 12), IRBB7 (lanes 4, 5, 13, and 14), and IRBB10 (lanes 6, 7, 15, and 16) grown in two hot spots for bacterial blight disease in the Philippines. The molecular markers (M) consist of a 1-kb ladder. The primers JEL1/JEL2 were used in the PCR method.

from naturally infected leaf samples of IR24 and near-isogenic lines (IRBB4, IRBB7, and IRBB10) planted in Calauan and Mabitac, two hot spots for bacterial blight disease in Laguna, Philippines. Different fingerprint patterns were detected from previously frozen, infected leaf samples analyzed by TCR using JEL1/JEL2 primers (Fig. 2). Since this method needs neither isolation nor cultivation of the pathogen, PCR of DNA from lesion exudates substantially reduces the time and resources required to fingerprint the bacterial blight pathogen, making it possible to conduct large-scale population studies in a cost-effective manner. ■

A method for estimating the number of eggs in egg masses of yellow stem borer

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Egg masses of yellow stem borer (YSB), *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), are multilayered and densely covered with hair. Consequently, it is not possible to count the number of eggs in an egg mass, either before or after the eggs have hatched. This results in difficulties in many studies of YSB behavior and host plant resistance in which plants or plots are artificially infested with egg masses, and where interpretation of results would be more powerful if the number of larvae hatching from the egg mass was known. This study demonstrates the accuracy of a method of egg number estimation that we have developed, based on comparison of test egg masses with a "reference collection."

Our reference collection consists of 50 YSB egg masses of varying size, for which we have recorded the actual number of hatching larvae (range: 30-150 larvae). Based on dissection of many other YSB egg masses after egg hatching, we have found that, in a healthy egg mass, almost all eggs will hatch. Therefore, the number of eggs in an egg mass is generally equivalent to the number of hatching larvae.

We collected YSB adults from rice-fields in the vicinity of IRRI and caged them on rice plants in a greenhouse. We obtained 95 egg masses and visually compared each one with our reference collection. The egg masses were placed individually in vials and the number of emerging larvae was recorded.

Based on visual comparison with the reference collection, our mean estimate was 104.2 ± 2.6 ($n = 95$) egg masses, a number very close to the mean number of larvae that we later observed to emerge from these egg masses, 104.9 ± 2.8 . The relationship between the number of estimated and observed eggs per egg mass, $y = 0.87x + 13.3$,

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Relation between estimated number of eggs and observed number of hatching larvae.

Parameter estimates for multiple regression of number of larvae per egg mass on egg mass length and width.

Variable	Estimate	SE	t ^a
Length	19.88	2.03	9.80**
Width	16.44	5.00	3.29**

^a** = significant at the 1% level.

where y is the estimated number, was linear and highly significant ($R^2 = 0.875$, $df = 93$, $P < 0.01$) (see figure). The regression indicates that we slightly overestimated the number of eggs in small egg masses and slightly underestimated the number in large egg masses.

Other researchers have used multiple regression equations to predict the number of eggs per YSB egg mass from measurements of egg mass length and width. To evaluate this method, we measured the length and width of our 95 test egg masses before egg hatch and used these measurements as indepen-

dent variables in a multiple linear regression, with the number of hatching larvae as the dependent variable. The resulting equation, $y = 19.881 + 16.44w - 56.96$ (see table), explained only 61% of the variation in the number of hatching larvae (adjusted $R^2 = 0.61$).

Our results demonstrate that, at least in the hands of an experienced researcher, comparison with a reference collection can be a highly accurate technique for estimating the number of eggs in a YSB egg mass. The predictive power of an alternative method, the multiple regression technique, could perhaps be improved by adding egg mass thickness as an additional independent variable. Maximum thickness of the egg mass could be measured with a set of calipers, but the variable thickness of the egg mass is better taken into account by visual comparison with a reference collection. ■

Excel modeling environment: description and application to the ORYZA0 model

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ORYZA0 is a N-limited rice production model developed at AB-DLO (Wageningen) during the SARP project, in collaborative work with IRRI and NARS from rice-producing countries in Asia. It was originally written in FST (Fortran Simulation Translator), within DOS. We have recently produced an Excel worksheet version. Three approaches were considered: direct, custom, and advanced. The main difference is the user interface. The direct approach (Fig. 1) uses a simple method containing few computations. This approach is useful as a teaching tool. The custom approach permits many relations among parameters. Emphasis is on a clear presentation of model input-output listings. Main input and output data are put together

Leaf photosynthesis explanatory model			
Parameter description	Dimension	Formula	Value
Intensity of absorbed radiation (PAR)	$J m^{-2} s^{-1}$		150
Max. leaf photosynthesis (at saturated light)	$kg CO_2 ha^{-1} h^{-1}$		50
Initial light use efficiency	$kg CO_2 ha^{-1} h^{-1}$		0.40
Gross photosynthesis rate	$J m^{-2} s^{-1}$	$D12 = D7 * (1 - EXP(-D9 * D5 / D7))$	34.94

1. Example of a simple model written in Excel. The direct approach is used. The four columns allow easy understanding of data and calculations.

while computation and less important parameters are hidden. This approach allows users to concentrate on model output and to identify knowledge gaps through simulations. The advanced approach is similar to the custom approach but makes more use of macros, modules, and Visual Basic. Colors, borders, text styles, buttons, and windows are used to provide a user-friendly interface. The interface accompanies the user in a model shell, and it is easy to scroll, with clear input requests, fast simulation run, and improved output. The advanced ap-

proach enlarges the user range for direct application, for demonstration, and for teaching purposes.

An example of Excel modeling environment using the advanced approach (Fig. 2) is the model ORYZA0.xls. A model like ORYZA0 is composed of initial variables, input tables, and equations. All these can be easily converted in a spreadsheet. The Fortran model functions were translated into the spreadsheet where in most of the cases the statements are the same

State variables, rate variables, driving variables, tables, and subrou-